

of these flavonoids along with their 3-*o*-rhamnosides and a biflavonoid, shows that the leaves of *R. mysorensis* is enriched with flavonoids and flavonoid glycosides in major amounts.

Experimental

1.5 kg shade dried leaves were successively extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), benzene and acetone. The vacuum dried acetone extract on alkali fractionation with (a) 2% Na₂CO₃ and (b) 2% NaOH solution, and neutralisation with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded a solid mixture containing several flavonoid components.

The three major flavonoids were separated by column chromatography (silica gel) of the ethyl acetate soluble portion of the above mixture using benzene-acetone (2 : 8, 5 : 5, 8 : 2) as eluent. The three flavonoids were purified by preparative paper chromatography using ethanol-acetic acid-water (40 : 13 : 30) as irrigating solvent.

Results and Discussion

The above flavonoids are identified as myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol by R_f value uv and ir, pmr and mass spectra of their acetates. The identity of the compounds was also confirmed by co-tlc using authentic specimens.

The higher R_f band of the solid mixture in ppc was further purified by preparative tlc (silica gel G) with benzene : pyridine : formic acid (40 : 10 : 2) and the major band was cut and eluted with pure methanol and recrystallised. It is identified as a biflavonoid containing two aepiginin units joined by a C—O—C linkage as 4'—0—6" which is identical to hinokiflavone. This is further confirmed by m.p., colour reactions and nmr data compared with an authentic specimen.

The methanol extract separated by column chromatography and the major eluent was evaporated with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate insoluble portion was separated and purified by preparative pc (40 : 13 : 30, ethanol-acetic acid-water) gave three flavonoid glycosides which were subjected to various colour reactions, uv fluorescence and hydrolysis and characterisation of hydrolytic products. All were found to be 3-*o*-glycosides and the single sugar was rhamnose. The aglycones were identified as myricetin, quercetin and kaempferol.

The identity of the three glycosides as Myricetin-3-*o*-rhamnoside, Quercetin-3-*o*-rhamnoside, and Kaempferol-3-*o*-rhamnoside was confirmed R_f, m.p. and λ_{max} by direct comparison with authentic samples. All the above compounds are isolated for the first time from this species.

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3-(1,1-Dimethylallyl) Xanthyletin from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng

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MURRAYA *koenigii* is known to be the richest source of carbazole alkaloids¹. Recent investigation reveals the presence of a coumarin from the petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the stem bark of *M. koenigii*. The coumarin has been identified as 3-(1,1-dimethylallyl) xanthyletin (I) which was previously isolated from *Boenninghausenia albifloar*².

The compound (I) (M⁺, 296), m.p. 100° was found homogeneous by tlc and mass spectrometry. It showed λ_{max}. (EtOH) 226, 267, 346 nm (log ε 4.3, 4.3 and 4.1); ν_{max}. (KBr) displayed peaks at 1720 (coumarin carbonyl) 1600, 1510 cm⁻¹ (aromatic); δ (100 MHz, solvent CDCl₃, standard Me₄Si), 7.4 (1H, s, C-4), 7.0 (1H, s, C-5), 6.72 (1H, s, C-8), 1.43 (12H, s, four methyl groups), 5.6 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 3'-H) and 6.3 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, 4'-H). The other signals consisted of an ABX system are (H_A, 5.03, q, J_{AX} 18 Hz; H_B, 5.08, q, J_{BX} 10Hz; H_X, 6.2, q, J_{AB} 1 Hz). The mass spectra of the compound showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 296. The base peak appeared at m/e 281 (M-15) represented by the ionic species (II). The other significant peak is at m/e 253 (M-15-28) (M⁺, Me-CO).

The production of formaldehyde in Lemieux-Rudoloff test³ supports the presence of a terminal methylene group in the side chain.

Finally the structure has been determined from ¹³C nmr (20 MHz, CDCl₃) detailed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—¹³C NMR OF COMPOUND (I)

Carbon no.	ppm	Carbon no.	ppm
2	159.7 s	2'	77.2 s
3	112.9 s	3'	120.8 d
4	145.4 d	4'	124.5 d
4a	118.2 s	1"	40.2 s
5	130.8 d	2"	137.4 d
6	131.5 s	3"	111.9 t
7	154.4 s		
8	103.4 d	1" < Me	25.9 q*
8a	155.8 s	2" < Me	28.0 q*

*Values may interchange.

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2-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-acetophenone Oxime as an Analytical Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Palladium

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2-Hydroxy-5-carboxy-acetophenone oxime (HCAO) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric determination of copper¹ and nickel². The present work describes the use of this ligand for the gravimetric determination of palladium(II). The reagent precipitates palladium ion at 0.8 and is quantitative between pH 1.5 to 3.0 and after drying at 110 to 120° the composition of the chelate corresponds to the formula Pd(C₉H₈O₄N)₂.

Experimental

Palladium chloride (1.0 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid and the solution was made to 500 ml. with distilled water.

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Preparation of reagent: *p*-Hydroxy-benzoic acid was acetylated³ and the resulting compound *p*-acetoxy-benzoic acid was converted into ketone by the following method⁴. *p*-Acetoxy-benzoic acid (3.0 g, 1 mol) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (7.0 g, 3.3 mol) were intimately mixed and heated on an oil bath at 150 to 155° protected by CaCl₂ guard tube for 1 h. The reaction mass was cooled and treated with ice and conc. HCl. The mass was washed and crystallised from ethanol to yield the resulting ketone, 2-hydroxy-5-carboxy-acetophenone⁴, m.p. 241°. The oxime was prepared by the reaction of the above ketone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate in aqueous ethanol. Crystallised from ethanol yielded the product, m.p. 258°d.

Determination of palladium(II) ion: A known volume (10 ml) of palladium ion solution was diluted to 70-80 ml and pH was adjusted to 1.5-2.0 using acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer. The solution was warmed to 60-70° and ethanolic solution of the reagent (1.0%) was added with constant stirring followed by about 10% excess to ensure complete precipitation. The yellow precipitate obtained was digested on water bath (60-80°) for 30 min. It was filtered and washed with hot water and finally with ethanol to remove any contamination of ligand from the complex.

The precipitate was dried at 110-120° and weighed as Pd(C₉H₈O₄N)₂. It is insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in pyridine, NaOH or NH₄OH solutions. Some of the results are given in Table 1. Conversion factor for Pd²⁺ is 0.2152.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II)

Pd(II) taken mg	Weight of complex mg	Pd(II) found mg	Error mg
12.28	57.30	12.33	+05
6.14	28.60	6.15	+01
9.82	45.50	9.85	+03
18.42	85.8	18.46	+04

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